

Supporting information

Improving Faradaic Efficiency for Conversion of Bicarbonate to Formate Using Indium-Bismuth Alloy Electrocatalysts

Yukun Hu^{1, #}, Yuke Li^{4, #}, Bingqing Yao², Guangxin Sun^{2, 3}, Fei Yu², Chunyang Chi¹, Caiwei Zhang¹, Tao Liu^{1, 3}, Panpan Zhang¹, Qian He², Jia Zhang^{4, *}, Andrew B. Wong^{1, 2, *}

¹ Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore, Engineering Drive 4, Singapore 117585

² Department of Materials Science and Engineering, National University of Singapore, Engineering Drive 1, Singapore 117575

³ Joint School of National University of Singapore and Tianjin University, International Campus of Tianjin University, Binhai New City, Fuzhou 350207, China

⁴ Institute of High Performance Computing (IHPC), Agency for Science, Technology, and Research (A*STAR), 138632, 1 Fusionopolis Way, #16-16 Connexis Singapore, Singapore

These authors contributed equally to this work

* Corresponding author

Author information

Corresponding Author

Andrew B. Wong —Assistant Professor, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore, Singapore. Email: mseabw@nus.edu.sg

Jia Zhang —Institute of High Performance Computing (IHPC), Agency for Science, Technology, and Research (A*STAR). Email: zhangji@ihpc.a-star.edu.sg

Authors

Yukun Hu — Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore, Singapore. Email: huyukun@u.nus.edu

Yuke Li —Institute of High Performance Computing (IHPC), Agency for Science, Technology, and Research (A*STAR). Email: li_yuke@ihpc.a-star.edu.sg

Bingqing Yao —Department of Materials Science and Engineering, National University of Singapore. Email: bq.yao@nus.edu.sg

Guangxin Sun — Department of Materials Science and Engineering, National University of Singapore; Joint School of the National University of Singapore and Tianjin University, International Campus of Tianjin University. Email: guangxin_sun@u.nus.edu

Fei Yu — Department of Materials Science and Engineering, National University of Singapore. Email: feiyu@u.nus.edu

Chunyang Chi — Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore. Email: chichunyang@u.nus.edu

Caiwei Zhang — Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore. Email: caiweizhang@u.nus.edu

Tao Liu — Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore; Joint School of National University of Singapore and Tianjin University, International Campus of Tianjin University. Email: e0787958@u.nus.edu

Panpan Zhang — Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of Singapore. Email: panpanz@u.nus.edu

Qian He —Assistant Professor, Department of Materials Science and Engineering,

Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, National University of
Singapore, Singapore. Email: hegian@nus.edu.sg

Experiment methods

Preparation of indium-bismuth alloys and electrodes

The bismuth oxide nanosheets (Bi_2O_3 NSs) were prepared by a hydrothermal method. First, 2 mmol $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.2 mmol cetrimonium bromide (CTAB) were dissolved in 20 mL 1.2 M acetic acid for 10 minutes to obtain the transparent solution. Then, 5.5 mL 6 M NaOH was continuously dropped into the solution under turbulent stirring until the PH value was 10.5, followed by 30 minutes of stirring for stabilization. Next, the creamy white solution was transferred to an autoclave for 8 h reaction under 160°C . The final solution was centrifuged to obtain the solid substances when the reaction finished. After five times of washing with deionized water and drying in an oven under 60°C overnight, the Bi_2O_3 NSs were obtained. The indium-bismuth oxide alloy (In- Bi_2O_3 NSs) was prepared with the same procedure except for the metal precursor, which is the mixture of $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{In}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Specifically, the 5 at%, 10 at%, and 15 at% indium samples (5% In Bi_2O_3 , 10% In Bi_2O_3 , and 15% In Bi_2O_3) were prepared with the amounts of indium precursor are 59.90 mg, 121.67 mg, and 181.57 mg, respectively. For electrode preparation, 12 mg bismuth oxide nanosheets were dissolved in 1 mL ethanol with 30 μl of Nafion solution for 30 minutes of sonication to get the ink solution. Then, the In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP electrodes were prepared by spray-coating the ink solution in the Freudenberg H23 $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ hydrophilic carbon paper. The SEM images and X-ray spectroscopy mapping results of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP electrodes are shown in Figure S19.

The indium-metallic bismuth nanoparticle electrodes (In-Bi NPs@CP) were prepared by electrochemical reduction of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP electrode in 0.5 M K_2SO_4 solution at -1.6 v vs. Ag/AgCl for 5 minutes. The indium-bismuth subcarbonate nanoplates electrodes (In- $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP) were prepared by electrochemical reduction of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP electrode in 3 M KHCO_3 solution at -1.6 v vs. Ag/AgCl for 5 minutes. Due to the turbulent electrolyte flow and phase transformation, some catalysts would

be flushed off from the electrodes, as shown in Figure S20. Therefore, a fresh electrode was applied for each current density to eliminate the influence of catalysts dropping off the support under electrolyte flushing.

Cell setup

H-Cell: The three-electrode system was employed to study the performance of In-Bi NPs@CP in an aqueous electrolyzer. In detail, the H-cell is composed of a cathode (catalyst-loaded Freudenberg H23 carbon paper), an anode (platinum foil), a reference electrode (3.5 M Ag/AgCl), and an anion exchange membrane (Fumasep FAS-50). Each electrode ($2 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) was prepared by spray-coating the ink solution (2.5 mg catalyst, 1 mL ethanol, and 30 μL Nafion solution) on the carbon paper. The active area of the electrode is $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ with a $1.2 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg}$ loading amount. For each experiment, 40 mL 0.1 M KHCO_3 solution was employed as both catholyte and anolyte without stirring. The CO_2 gas flow was continuously supplied to the catholyte with a flow rate of $20 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, and each experiment would not start until after 20 minutes of CO_2 saturation. The applied potential was recorded against Ag/AgCl and then converted to RHE with iR compensation as the following eq (1):

$$E_{RHE} = E_{Ag/AgCl} + 0.197 + 0.0591 \times pH - iR \quad (1)$$

where E_{RHE} denotes the potential for reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE); $E_{AgCl/Ag}$ is the applied potential; pH is the basicity of the electrolyte; i is the current recorded by potentiostat; R is the resistance of the cell.

MEA cell: The two-electrode system was employed to investigate the performance of bicarbonate electrolysis. Specifically, the MEA cell (5 cm^2 cell hardware, Fuel Cell Technologies) consists of two stainless steel housing, a PTFE 4 cm^2 gasket, two graphitic serpentine channels, and a membrane electrode assembly (MEA). The MEA consists of a cathode (with catalyst loaded onto Freudenberg H23 carbon paper), a Ni foam anode, and a bipolar membrane (Fumasep FBM-PK). Each electrode ($2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$) was prepared by spray-coating the ink solution (12.5 mg catalyst, 1 mL ethanol,

and 30 μL Nafion solution) on the carbon paper. The electrodes' active area (masked by a PTFE gasket) is $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ with a $1.5 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg}$ loading amount. 80 mL 3 M KHCO_3 solution and 80 mL 1 M KOH were fed as the catholyte and anolyte, respectively, with the rate of $50 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ (by Masterflex L/S peristaltic pump). The headspace of the outer electrolyte reservoir was purged with N_2 to the GC for detecting gas products with an N_2 flow rate of $20 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

Product quantification

The formate product was quantified using a Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectrometer (Bruker 400 MHz system). The internal standard was prepared by dissolving 0.0988g phenol and 2.98 μL dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) in 20 mL D_2O . Each electrolyte aliquot (700 μL) was mixed with 35 μL internal standard for NMR testing with water suppressing technique. The calibration curve for quantitative analysis was prepared by plotting the peak area (x-axis) with specific product concentration (y-axis). For formate in 0.1 M KHCO_3 solution, 0.01 mM, 0.05 mM, 0.1 mM, 0.25 mM, 0.5 mM, 1 mM, 5 mM, and 10 mM formate solution was mixed with internal standard for calibration curve preparation (Figure S18a). For formate in 3 M KHCO_3 solution, 0.5 mM, 1 mM, 5 mM, 10 mM, 25 mM, 50 mM, 100 mM, and 200 mM formate solution was mixed with an internal standard for calibration curve preparation (Figure S18b). The NMR result is shown in Figure S18c.

The gas sample was purged out from the headspace of the outer electrolyte reservoir into a gas chromatography instrument (GC Shimadzu, 2014) every 12 minutes. The GC is equipped with two packed columns, one methanizer flame ionization detector (MTNFID), one split/splitless injector flame ionization detector (SPLFID), and one thermal conductivity detector (TCD). MTNFID and TCD are responsible for CO and H_2 quantification, respectively.

Characterization

The electrolysis experiments were conducted by a Biologic VMP 300 potentiostat with 2 A/30V booster for chronoamperometry and chronopotentiometry in a MEA cell and H-cell. X-ray diffraction (XRD) characterization was carried out with Shimadzu XRD-6000 in the range of 2θ angles of 10° to 90° with a step size of 0.04° and a step time of 0.6 s. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) testing was performed in JEOL JSM-7610F field scanning electron microscope with accelerating voltage from 5 keV to 15 eV. The microscopy images were taken under 5 keV, while the energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping results were obtained under 15 keV. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) testing was performed in JEM-2100, equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray analyzer. Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) was performed in JEOL JEM-2800, equipped with an EDS function. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) characterization was performed in Kratos AXIS Ultra XPS with an X-ray source of Mono Al K α under 5×10^{-9} Torr. The survey scan was conducted between 1100-5 eV with the step of 1 eV and sweep of 1. The narrow scan was completed for specific elements with the step of 0.05 eV and a 100-400 ms dwell time. All the spectrum was calibrated C 1s (C-C bond) to 284.50 eV. The atomic ratio for specific elements was calculated by XPS quantitative analysis via eq (2). The sensitive factor (SF) of Bi 4d, O 1s, and In 4d are 4.405, 0.78, and 0.284, respectively.

$$Atomic\ Ratio\% = \frac{\frac{Area}{(Sensitive\ Factor)_1}}{\frac{Area}{(Sensitive\ Factor)_1} + \frac{Area}{(Sensitive\ Factor)_2} + \frac{Area}{(Sensitive\ Factor)_3} + \dots} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

ECSA testing and LSV testing

Each electrode's electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) was determined by cyclic voltammetry scanning from -0.4 v to -0.5 v vs. Ag/AgCl (non-faradaic range) after the CO₂ reduction reaction was completed 15 times. Six different scanning rates (i.e., 20 mv·s⁻¹, 40 mv·s⁻¹, 60 mv·s⁻¹, 80 mv·s⁻¹, 100 mv·s⁻¹, 120 mv·s⁻¹) were plotted against the corresponding non-faradaic current density to get the slope that corresponds to the catalyst capacitance (Figure S8a-S8d). Then, the same procedure was applied to pure Freudenberg H23 carbon paper to get the other capacitance. The ECSA was obtained from the quotient between electrode and carbon paper capacitance.

The LSV testing was conducted in a three-electrode system consisting of a cathode, Pt, and Ag/AgCl electrodes. The experiments were performed after N₂ saturation for 30 minutes. The scan range is from -0.4 v to -1.8 v vs. Ag/AgCl, with a scan rate of 20 mv·s⁻¹.

Computational Method

First-principles calculations were carried out within the density functional theory framework. The projector-augmented wave (PAW)^[1] method and the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) for the exchange-correlation energy functional, as implemented in the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP)^[2-3] were used. The GGA calculation was performed with the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation potential.^[4] A plane-wave cutoff energy of 400 eV was used. Grimmes's DFT-D3 dispersion correction was used to describe the van der Waals interaction.^[5] Structural optimization was conducted for bulk Bi and Bi₂O₂CO₃. For bulk Bi, the optimized lattice constants are determined to be $a = b = 4.55 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 11.87 \text{ \AA}$, where the experimental lattice constant is $a=b=4.54 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=11.86 \text{ \AA}$. In the case of bulk Bi₂O₂CO₃, the lattice constants are found to be $a = 3.57 \text{ \AA}$, $b=4.52 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=13.77 \text{ \AA}$ where the experimental lattice constant is $a = 3.59 \text{ \AA}$, $b=4.55 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=13.88 \text{ \AA}$. In surface calculations of Bi, a 3-layer Bi (012) surface model utilizing a 2×2 supercell is employed, where the k-mesh is set to 4×4×1. For Bi₂O₂CO₃ surface calculations, a two-layer surface model with a 2×4 supercell is used, accompanied by a 3×2×1 k-mesh. On the Bi (012) surface, the bottom two layers are held fixed, while for the Bi₂O₂CO₃ surface, only the bottom layer is fixed. Additionally, the thickness of the vacuum layer is maintained at 15 Å. During the relaxation process, the atoms are adjusted until the total energy reaches a tolerance of 1×10^{-5} eV, ensuring that the forces on each atom are kept below 0.02 eV/Å. Transition state searches are conducted using the climbing image nudged elastic band method^[6], with a force threshold of less than 0.05 eV/Å. The

frequency of the transition state was determined to ensure only one imaginary frequency. The dipole correction is considered in the whole calculation.^[7]

For the reconstruction of the $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) surface, the process was as follows:

1. Initial Optimization: The layer structure of $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) was first optimized to ensure a stable starting point for further simulations.
2. Thermal Annealing Simulation: Following the initial optimization, a thermal annealing simulation was conducted at 300K over a period of 20 ps with a time step of 2 fs and only one gamma point.
3. Post-Annealing Optimization: After the thermal annealing, the $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) surface undergoes another round of optimization.

For the reconstruction of the $\text{In-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) surface, the approach incorporates a specific substitution and optimization process:

1. Substitution and Initial Configuration Generation: In the layer $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) structure, one In atom replaced one Bi atom. Accompanying this substitution, three different O vacancy locations were identified, leading to three distinct configurations. This step was foundational for exploring the effects of In incorporation on the surface structure.
2. Optimization of Configurations: Each of the three generated configurations underwent optimization in Figure S34, ensuring that they represented stable possible states of the $\text{In-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ surface.
3. Thermal Annealing and Final Optimization of the Most Stable Configuration: The most stable configuration identified from the initial optimizations is subjected to thermal annealing and subsequent optimization. This process aims to achieve the final reconstructed structure named $\text{R}_{\text{In-V}_\text{O}}\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3(001)$.

For free energy calculations, all of the first layer Bi atoms and In atoms were considered as the adsorption sites. The most reactive site was used to calculate $U_{\text{L}}(\text{CO}_2\text{RR})$ and $U_{\text{L}}(\text{HER})$ to analyze the selectivity.

The Hydrogen adsorption free energy $\Delta G(\text{H}^*)$ calculation is defined as:

$$\Delta G(H^*) = G(H^*) - G(*) - 1/2G(H_2) \quad (3)$$

where $G(H^*)$, $G(*)$, and $G(H_2)$ are the free energy of surface adsorbed with H atom, slab, and H_2 molecule, respectively.

The formation energy of D_{Bi} -Bi(012) is defined as following:

$$\Delta E = E(D_{Bi} - Bi (012)) - E(Bi (012)) - E(Bi) \quad (4)$$

where $E(D_{Bi}$ -Bi (012)) and $E(Bi (012))$ are the potential energy of D_{Bi} -Bi (012) and Bi (012), respectively. $E(Bi)$ is the energy of the Bi atom.

The formation energy of R_{In} -Bi (012) is defined as follows:

$$\Delta E = E(R_{In} - Bi (012)) + E(Bi) - E(Bi (012)) - E(In) \quad (5)$$

where $E(R_{In}$ -Bi (012)) is the potential energy of R_{In} -Bi (012). $E(In)$ is the energy of the In atom. The formation energy of D_{In} -Bi (012) is defined as follows:

$$\Delta E = E(D_{In} - Bi (012)) - E(Bi (012)) - E(In) \quad (6)$$

where $E(D_{In}$ -Bi(012)) is the potential energy of D_{In} -Bi(012).

The formation energy of D_{Bi} -Bi(012) is -2.22eV. The configurations formation energy of R_{In} -Bi(012) and D_{In} -Bi(012) is 0.44eV and -2.37eV, respectively. For the formate formation reaction, the reactions are in the following:

The adsorption energies of $\Delta G(*OCHO)$ is calculated with the following equation.

$$\Delta G([*]OCHO) = G([*]OCHO) - G(CO_2) - G(*) - 0.5G(H_2) \quad (9)$$

where $G(*)$ is the energy of the surface. $G(CO_2)$ and $G(H_2)$ are the energy of CO_2 and H_2 molecules at standard conditions. $G(*OCHO)$ is the energy of the surface adsorbed with $*OCHO$.

The Gibbs free energies (G) at 298.15 K and 1 atm are calculated by:

$$G = E + ZPE - TS \quad (10)$$

where E is the potential energy obtained from DFT calculations, ZPE and S are the contributions to the free energy from the zero point vibration energy and entropy, respectively. T is the temperature (298K). $G(H^+ + e^-)$ is considered as the half of free energy $G(H_2)$.

The limiting potentials (U_L) of CO₂RR are defined as

$$U_L = -\frac{\Delta G_{max}}{e} = -\frac{\max\{\Delta G_1, \Delta G_2\}}{e} \quad (11)$$

where ΔG_1 and ΔG_2 are the free energy changes of eq (7) and eq (8), respectively.

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1. (a) SEM images of In-Bi₂O₃ NPs@CP (Inset figure: Higher magnification image). (b) SEM images of In-Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP (Inset figure: Higher magnification image). (c) TEM image of In-Bi₂O₃ NSs. (d) TEM image of In-Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs. (e) The optical image of In-Bi₂O₃ NSs@CP (left), In-Bi NPs@CP (middle), and In-Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP (right). (f) Logic flow chart of material synthesis.

Figure S2. Pourbaix diagram of bismuth (upper) and indium (lower).

Figure S3. (a) XRD pattern of In-Bi₂O₃ NSs@CP. (b) XRD pattern of In-Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP.

Figure S4. (a) X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of In-Bi NPs@CP. (b) X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of In-Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP.

Figure S5. TEM images and EDS mapping of 10% In Bi_2O_3 NSs. (b) TEM images and EDS mapping of 5% In Bi NPs. (c) TEM images and EDS mapping of 5% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NSs.

Figure S6. (a) FE_{formate} comparison among pure Bi NPs@CP, 10%In Bi NPs@CP, and 15% In Bi NPs@CP in BRR. (b) FE_{H_2} comparison between pure Bi NPs@CP and 5% In Bi NPs@CP in BRR. (c) FE_{H_2} comparison among pure Bi NPs@CP, 10% In Bi NPs@CP, and 15% In Bi NPs@CP in BRR. (d-f) FE_{HCOOH} , FE_{H_2} , and FE_{CO} summary for pure Bi NPs@CP, 5% In Bi NPs@CP, 10% In Bi NPs@CP, and 15% In Bi NPs@CP in H-Cell.

Figure S7. XPS Bi 4d and In 3d narrow spectrum of In-Bi NPs@CP samples after the reaction. (a)-(e) 5% In Bi NPs@CP after reaction at $V_{RHE} = -0.86$ v, $V_{RHE} = -0.93$ v, $V_{RHE} = -1.0$ v, $V_{RHE} = -1.1$ v, and $V_{RHE} = -1.2$ v, respectively. (f)-(j) 10% In Bi NPs@CP after reaction at $V_{RHE} = -0.86$ v, $V_{RHE} = -0.93$ v, $V_{RHE} = -1.0$ v, $V_{RHE} = -1.1$ v, and $V_{RHE} = -1.2$ v, respectively. (k)-(o) 15% In Bi NPs@CP after reaction at $V_{RHE} = -0.86$ v, $V_{RHE} = -0.93$ v, $V_{RHE} = -1.0$ v, $V_{RHE} = -1.1$ v, and $V_{RHE} = -1.2$ v, respectively.

Figure S8. Typical effective electrochemical active surface area testing. (a) Cyclic voltammetry for pure Bi NPs@CP with scan rate from 20 mV·s⁻¹ to 120 mV·s⁻¹. (b) Cyclic voltammetry for 5% In Bi NPs@CP with scan rate from 20 mV·s⁻¹ to 120 mV·s⁻¹. (c) Cyclic voltammetry for carbon paper with scan rate from 20 mV·s⁻¹ to 120 mV·s⁻¹. (d) ECSA for pure Bi NPs@CP, 5% In Bi NPs@CP, and carbon paper. (e) LSV curves of In-Bi NPs@CP in N₂ saturated 0.1M KHCO₃ solution. (f) The normalized partial current density of In-Bi NPs@CP for formate in H-cell.

Figure S9. Tafel slope in N₂ saturated 3M KHCO₃ solution to evaluate rate-determining step of HER. (a) In-Bi NPs@CP. (b) In-Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP. (c) In-Bi₂O₃ NSs@CP.

Figure S10. (a) FE_{formate} of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP in MEA. (b) FE_{H_2} of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP in MEA. (c) FE_{CO} of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP in MEA.

Figure S11. LSV curves of In- Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP in N_2 saturated 3M KHCO_3 solution.

Figure S12. (a) XRD patterns of pure Bi NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (b) XRD patterns of 5% In Bi NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (c) XRD patterns of 15% In Bi NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities.

Figure S13. (a) XRD patterns pure Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (b) XRD patterns of 5% In Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (c) XRD patterns of 10% In Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities.

Figure S14. (a) FE_{formate} comparison among pure Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, 10% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, and 15% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP. (b) FE_{H2} comparison among pure Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, 5% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, 10% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, and 15% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP. (c) FE_{CO} comparison among pure Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, 5% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, 10% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP, and 15% In Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP.

Figure S15. (a) XRD patterns of pure $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (b) XRD patterns of 5% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (c) XRD patterns of 10% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities. (d) XRD patterns of 15% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP after galvanostatic operation in MEA at different current densities.

Figure S16. XPS spectra of oxygen 1s for pure $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP, 5% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP, 10% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP, and 15% In $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP, respectively. The peak at 531 eV represents oxygen vacancy.^[8]

Figure S17. Performance comparison. (a) FE_{formate} under different partial current densities in BRR, aqueous CO₂RR (in H-cell), and gaseous CO₂RR (in flow cell and MEA). (b) The formate production rate in BRR, aqueous CO₂RR (in H-cell), and gaseous CO₂RR (in the flow cell and MEA)

Figure S18. The calibration curve of formate in (a) 0.1 M KHCO₃ and (b) 3 M KHCO₃. (c) NMR spectrum of liquid products for 5% In Bi NPs@CP sample after 30 minutes of electrolysis at 400 mA·cm⁻².

Figure S19. (a) SEM-EDS mapping for the selected area. (b) TEM image of hydrothermally synthesized Bi_2O_3 NSs. (c)-(f) SEM-EDS mappings for image (a). (g) EDS spectrum of the scanned area.

Figure S20. (a) Catalyst dropping off the support under the electrolyte flushing of Bi_2O_3 NSs@CP electrodes. (b) SEM image of the black substances in Figure (a). (c) No catalyst dropping off for $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ NPs@CP electrodes. (d) Image of MEA system.

Figure S21. Free energy profiles of HER on (a) Bi (012), (b) D_{Bi} -Bi (012), (c)-(d) R_{In} -Bi (012), (e) D_{In} -Bi (012). (a)-(e): correspond directly to structures in Figure S27, establishing a one-to-one relationship between the observed binding sites and the structural configurations from that figure.

Figure S22. Free energy profiles of CO₂RR to format on (a) Bi (012), (b) D_{Bi}-Bi (012), (c) R_{In}-Bi (012), (d) D_{In}-Bi (012). (a)-(d): correspond directly to structures in Figure S28, establishing a one-to-one relationship between the observed binding sites and the structural configurations from that figure.

Figure S23. Free energy profiles of water dissociation on Bi system. The structures of Bi (012) and D_{Bi}-Bi (012) are illustrated in Figure S29. The structures of R_{In}-Bi (012) and D_{In}-Bi (012) are illustrated in Figure S30.

Figure S24. Free energy profiles of HER on Bi₂O₂CO₃(001). (a)-(f) represents different binding sites. The structures of (a)-(c) are illustrated in Figure S33, and the structures of (d)-(f) are illustrated in Figure S34.

Figure S25. Free energy profiles of CO₂RR to formate on Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001). (a)-(i) represents different binding sites. The structures of (a)-(c) are in Figure S35, The structures of (d)-(f) are in Figure S36, and The structures of (g)-(i) are in Figure S37.

Figure S26. Free energy profiles of HER on $R_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001). (a)-(h) represents different binding sites. The structures of (a)-(c) are in Figure S38; The structures of (d)-(f) are in Figure S39; The structures of (g)-(h) are in Figure S40.

Figure S27. Free energy profiles of CO₂RR to formate on R_{ln}-V_o-Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001). (a)-(i) represents different binding sites. (a)-(c) correspond directly to structures in Figure S41. (d)-(f) correspond directly to structures in Figure S42. (g)-(i) correspond directly to structures depicted in Figure S43.

Figure S28. Free energy profiles of water dissociation on Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001) and R_{In}-V_O-Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001), respectively. The structures of adsorbates on Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001) are illustrated in Figure S44, and the structures of adsorbates on R_{In}-V_O-Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001) are illustrated in Figure S45.

Figure S29. Top and side view of optimized *H binding structure. (a)-(b) Bi (012), (c)-(d) D_{Bi}-Bi (012), (e)-(h) R_{In}-Bi (012) and (i)-(j) D_{In}-Bi (012).

Figure S30. Top and side view of optimized *OCHO binding structure. (a-b) Bi (012), (c)-(d) D_{Bi} -Bi (012), (e)-(f) R_{In} -Bi (012), (g)-(h) D_{In} -Bi (012).

Figure S31. Top and side view of water dissociation structures on Bi (012) and D_{Bi-Bi} (012), respectively. H_2O : (a)-(b), (g-h); transition state: (c)-(d), (i-j); $H^+ + OH^*$: (e)-(f), (k)-(l).

Figure S32. Top and side view of water dissociation structures on $R_n\text{-Bi}$ (012) and $D_{ln}\text{-Bi}$ (012), respectively. H_2O : (a)-(b), (g)-(h); transition state: (c)-(d), (i)-(j); H^+OH^* : (e)-(f), (k)-(l).

Figure S33. Top and side view of configurations. (a)-(b) Initial $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001), (c)-(d) optimized $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001). After the geometry optimization, the layer structure remains.

Figure S34. Top and side view of optimized configurations with different O vacancy sites. (a)-(b) configuration 1 (relative energy: 0.00 eV), (c)-(d) configuration 2 (relative energy: -2.31 eV), (e)-(f) configuration 3 (relative energy: -3.74 eV). Configuration 3 is the most stable, named $R_{In-V_6-Bi_2O_2CO_3}$ (001).

Figure S35. Top and side view of optimized *H binding on $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (a)-(c) of Figure S22.

Figure S36. Top and side view of optimized $*\text{H}$ binding on $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (d)-(f) of Figure S22.

Figure S37. Top and side view of optimized *OCHO binding structure corresponding to the free energy profiles of (a)-(c) of Figure S23.

Figure S38. Top and side view of optimized *OCHO binding structure corresponding to the free energy profiles of (d)-(f) of Figure S23.

Figure S39. Top and side view of optimized *OCHO binding structure corresponding to the free energy profiles of (g)-(i) of Figure S23.

Figure S40. Top and side view of optimized *H binding on $R_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (a)-(c) of Figure S24.

Figure S41. Top and side view of optimized *H binding on $R_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (d)-(f) of Figure S24.

Figure S42. Top and side view of optimized H^* binding on $\text{R}_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (g)-(i) of Figure S24.

Figure S43. Top and side view of optimized $*\text{OCHO}$ binding on $\text{R}_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (a)-(c) of Figure S25.

Figure S44. Top and side view of optimized $*\text{OCHO}$ binding on $\text{R}_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (d)-(f) of Figure S25.

Figure S45. Top and side view of optimized $*\text{OCHO}$ binding on $\text{R}_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001) corresponding to the free energy profiles of (g)-(i) of Figure S25.

Figure S46. Top and side view of water dissociation structures on $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001). H_2O : (a)-(b); transition state: (c)-(d); H^+ + OH^- : (e)-(f).

Figure S47. Top and side view of water dissociation structures on $R_{1n}\text{-V}_o\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (001). H_2O : (a)-(b); transition state: (c)-(d); H^*+OH^* : (e)-(f).

Supplemental Tables

Table S1. The potential determining step of CO₂RR on Bi (012), D_{Bi}-Bi (012), R_{In}-Bi (012) and D_{In}-Bi (012).

Systems	Potential determining step
Bi(012)	CO ₂ +H ⁺ +e ⁻ →*OCHO
D _{Bi} -Bi(012)	CO ₂ +H ⁺ +e ⁻ →*OCHO
R _{In} -Bi(012)	CO ₂ +H ⁺ +e ⁻ →*OCHO
D _{In} -Bi(012)	CO ₂ +H ⁺ +e ⁻ →*OCHO

Table S2. The potential determining step of CO₂RR on Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001) and R_{in}-V_o-Bi₂O₂CO₃ (001).

Systems	Potential determining step
Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃ (001)	CO ₂ +H ⁺ +e ⁻ → *OCHO
R _{in} -V _o -Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃ (001)	*OCHO+H ⁺ +e ⁻ →* + HCOOH

Table S3. Peak area summary for In-Bi₂O₃ NSs@CP, In-Bi NPs@CP, and Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP samples, respectively.

No	Sample	Bi 4f area	SF	In 4d area	SF	O 1s area	SF
1	5% In Bi ₂ O ₃	44124		279.77		8319.31	
		31592.43		205.02		6554.1	
		37172.36		188.12		8156.87	
2	10% In Bi ₂ O ₃	29593.07		466.23		6574.22	
		20058.45		320.99		5085.43	
		33504.72		367.34		7689.15	
3	15% In Bi ₂ O ₃	29768.62		646.93		6324.50	
		30972.75		636.92		7890.92	
		36326.91		709.2		7837.42	
4	5% In Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	26737.09		149.80		5782.23	
		633.67		12.36		526.95	
		634.64		527.88		14.47	
5	10% In Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	314.8		12.63		256.26	
		32313.51	9.14	294.86	0.284	7168.56	0.78
		23789.2		258.98		5664.99	
6	15% In Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	114931.04		532.53		5176.2	
		15591.72		544.67		6032.17	
		315.25		30.26		527.09	
7	5% In Bi	14931.04		149.20		3408.71	
		35591.09		277.23		7998.88	
		39239.2		195.17		8236.84	
8	10% In Bi	32294.88		416.38		7694.93	
		33504.72		367.34		7689.15	
		20058.45		320.99		5085.43	
9	15% In Bi	11596.53		459.61		3951.52	
		14113.49		532.53		5176.2	
		29131.11		457.96		5560	

Table S4. Quantitative analysis of indium content of In-Bi₂O₃ NSs@CP, In-Bi NPs@CP, and Bi₂O₂CO₃ NPs@CP samples, respectively.

No	sample	Bi Atomic %	In Atomic %	O Atomic %
1	5% In Bi ₂ O ₃	27.85 ± 1.30	5.36 ± 0.87	66.66 ± 2.26
2	10% In Bi ₂ O ₃	23.78 ± 1.31	10.85 ± 1.88	65.36 ± 1.76
3	15% In Bi ₂ O ₃	23.15 ± 1.41	15.35 ± 1.24	61.49 ± 2.47
4	5% In Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	14.80 ± 10.49	5.62 ± 0.82	79.57 ± 9.83
5	10% In Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	19.43 ± 9.54	8.79 ± 1.74	71.59 ± 7.82
6	15% In Bi ₂ O ₂ CO ₃	11.53 ± 6.33	16.18 ± 2.86	72.27 ± 9.11
7	5% In Bi	26.13 ± 1.34	6.30 ± 1.82	67.56 ± 0.55
8	10% In Bi	23.6 ± 1.23	10.02 ± 1.38	66.37 ± 0.15
9	15% In Bi	19.34 ± 6.39	17.50 ± 3.55	63.15 ± 3.15

Table S5. Performance comparison summary among BRR, CO₂RR (in H-cell), and CO₂RR (in flow cell).

Catalyst	Reaction type	Cell type	Catholyte	Current density (mA·cm ⁻²)	Formate FE (%)	Formate generation rate (mmol·L ⁻¹ ·cm ⁻² ·h ⁻¹)	Ref.
This work	BRR	MEA	3M KHCO ₃	60	84.81	11.86	This work
				100	83.67	19.51	
				200	77.25	36.02	
				300	60.4	42.25	
				400	60.24	56.19	
ED-Bi	BRR	MEA	3M KHCO ₃	100	62	14.45	[9]
				400	27	25.18	
SnO ₂ /C	BRR	MEA	3M KHCO ₃	100	58	4.16	[10]
				400	38	15.76	
ED-Bi	BRR	MEA	2.5M NH ₄ HCO ₃	300	57	26.58	[11]
			2.5M KHCO ₃	300	47	21.92	
Bi NTs	CO ₂ RR	H-Cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	43.7	90	/	[12]
Bi _{0.1} Sn	CO ₂ RR	Flow Cell	1.0 M KHCO ₃	100	95	/	[13]
Sn	CO ₂ RR	MEA	CO ₂ + Vapor	55.4	93.3	11.95	[14]
SnO ₂ -GDEs	CO ₂ RR	Flow Cell	0.5 M KCl + 0.45 M KHCO ₃	300	44.9	39.13	[15]
Bi-Sn	CO ₂ RR	H-Cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	45	96	18.5	[16]
Sn _{1-x} Bi _x	CO ₂ RR	Flow Cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	77.87	95.8	10.20	[17]
Bismuthene	CO ₂ RR	H-Cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	18.18	99	6.71	[18]
SnS	CO ₂ RR	H-Cell	0.5 M KHCO ₃	44.7	92.6	28.6	[19]
Bi ₂ S ₃ -derived	CO ₂ RR	Flow Cell	1.0 M KOH	2000	93	/	[20]
In/N-dG	CO ₂ RR	Flow Cell	1.0 M KOH	1200	96	/	[21]
InBi	CO ₂ RR	Flow Cell	1.0 M KOH	300	85	/	[22]

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